

LEARNING TECHNOLOGY ACCELERATOR

LEA

D 2.4 Impact on Learning Analytics and Methodology for
living labs
30.10.2019

Project acronym: LEA

Project title: Learning Technology Accelerator

Grant Agreement number: 779803

Coordinator: Jyväskylän Yliopisto

Project funded by the European Commission,
H2020

Funding Scheme: H2020-ICT-2017-1

Due date of deliverable:	31/10/2019
Actual submission date:	31/10/2019
Start date of the project:	March 1, 2018
Project duration:	24 months

Workpackage	2
Task(s)	D 2.4 Impact on Learning Analytics and Methodology for living labs
Lead beneficiary	City of Torino
Editor/ authors	Elena Deambrogio, Laura Ribotta, Federico Cuomo, Jari Laru
Quality reviewers	António Soares Direito (Braga Municipality), Rikard Ström (GR), Anna-Maria Nurmi (Konnevesi High School)

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
----	--------	---

PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including	
O	the Commission Services)	

This publication reflects only the views of the author. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	INTRODUCTION	5
2.	METHODOLOGY	5
2.1.	LEA School Labs	6
2.1.a	User engagement methodology	6
3.	TORINO CITY LAB	13
4.	CALL EDULAB	15
4.1.	From needs to testing: a call to spread the LEA strategy	17
4.2.	Guidelines to apply Edulab call	17
4.3.	Lessons learnt for LEA partners from Edulab call experience	19
5.	Technical infrastructures needed for an educational living lab	22
5.1.	Tecnical infrastructures and furnishings of EDULAB in Torino	24
5.2.	The partner network of Torino City Lab	27
6.	Conclusions	30
	<i>Annex 1: Call Edulab: rules of participation</i>	33
	<i>Annex 2: Call Edulab: request of participation</i>	38
	<i>Annex 3: Call Edulab: questions for the form on line</i>	40
	<i>Annex 4: Call Edulab: grid for evaluation</i>	42
	<i>Annex 5: Call Edulab: agreement</i>	44
	<i>Annex 6: Lesson learnt questionnaire</i>	52

1. INTRODUCTION

LEA School Labs are classrooms across Europe open for learntech testing affiliated by LEA project. Currently LEA School Labs operate in Finland, Sweden, Germany, Spain, Portugal and Italy in real classroom environments.

The LEA School Labs are thought as a dedicated environment where to allow businesses/experts/professionals to co-develop and test innovative solutions in real life conditions and in collaboration with final users.

The LEA School Labs are open to include primary, secondary and upper secondary students and teachers.

As partner of LEA project, Torino is developing an inclusive strategy to connect companies, teachers and students in the field of new learning technologies.

In order to give the strategy a practical aspect, the City of Torino has decided to use the school lab as a tool able to respond to the needs of teachers and students emerged in LEA schools analysis by proposing new solutions provided by the private sector. The framework elaborated and implemented by Turin will be deeply analysed in this deliverable and shared among partners, in order to let them to evaluate its attractiveness in their local context and to take into consideration potential replicability, partially or as a whole.

2. METHODOLOGY

The City of Torino has decided to structure the school laboratory starting from the needs and requirements highlighted by students and teachers of the city territory during LEA needs analysis.

To address this interest, the City conducted a questionnaire involving three schools (survey conducted by all procurer partners in October 2018, results in D 3.4).

This questionnaire, shared among all LEA procurers partners and duly filled-in order to gather and deepen final users' needs, was used to set up a set of targeted workshops involving directly the final users to explore their needs; in the case of Turin, the workshop (D 3.4) took place in October 2018 and involved 1 selected middle school.

Starting from the results of the questionnaire, the City of Torino started to design an Educational Lab that, on the one hand, would be part of the wider strategy of the Torino City Lab and, on the other hand, would be able to follow up the experience of LEA school Labs.

2.1. LEA School Labs

Starting from the questionnaires (inquadrare a quali questionari si fa riferimento, v. su: WP/task nel quale erano stati sviluppati – oggetto – destinatari – eventualmente, esiti) carried out in recent months by LEA partners, the aim is to carry out a strategy shared by the different cities involved.

In order to explain the basis on which the LEA intervention is based, it is necessary to clarify and compare the current situations of the LEA school Labs in different contexts.

In this section, we are going to present:

- a) the main suggestions expressed by the partners about the user engagement methodology
- b) the current features of the ongoing LEA School Labs

2.1.a User engagement methodology

The partners made some comments about the involvement of users and the choice of the approach to be used to present technologies in schools.

First of all, the need to involve the technology promoters themselves during the workshops was stressed. This strategy is considered key to establish a direct and clear link between suppliers and users of services. It was also pointed out that this link should be created from the earliest stages of the Living Lab.

Secondly, the importance of structuring an effective call for interest to set up a living lab on education as in Turin was stressed. This has to be suitable for the local context as clear in specifying the objectives of Learning Technologies.

Furthermore, it was highlighted the crucial role played by the teachers. They should be prepared to lead the students in the technologies experimentation.

Another key factor at methodological level was identified in the collection of data and questionnaires related to workshops conducted in schools. A shared methodology of collection has to be adopted within a summary protocol on the details of each School Living Labs. What emerged from this LEA activity has been used to structure and/or/improve LEA schools labs. In particular, for Turin, the needs analysis and questionnaires results have been used as a base to structure the City EDULAB call.

Finally, the need emerged to clarify which supports are necessary for each technology that is expected to be adopted during the Living Labs. This action has to be conducted with the users (students and teachers) to fulfill every possible lack and necessity depending on the contexts of experimentation.

2.1.b Current features of the ongoing LEA School Labs

Torino sent a questionnaire to all procurer partners to compare the different school labs among the LEA project and to put in evidence

common points or different approaches. The results of this survey is described in the following paragraph.

Turin (Italy)

Schools	Students	Teachers	Age range
3	60	12	6-14

Description

In Torino a school (situated in via Bardonecchia) will be the LEA School Lab's center and it will become an environment available for all schools, but also a new school building concept, opened to the citizens. This building hosts a secondary school (students aged 11-14) and it is thought to become an open space for the local community even outside the school time and for all the schools of the metropolitan area interested in testing new technologies.

Technical equipments available:

- Theater Laboratory: 50 square meters space, stage, lighting and sound management systems for theater performances.
- Cinema Laboratory: editing rooms (PC and video cameras), cinema hall (maxi-screen for digital cinema projection), multimedia archive (movie files and DVDs).
- Other thematic spaces during the design phase.

What Torino offers to companies/experts: facilitation for paperwork and contacts with public bodies; a real place for testing and visibility thanks to websites and networks.

According to the experience of Torino Living Lab the LEA School Lab will have the following administrative steps:

- call for testing for business companies, this guarantees transparency in identifying companies;
- evaluation commission, in this case they can also include representatives of the users (e.g. teachers) as well as the procurers;
- an experimentation agreement (Annex 5) is made for the regulation of commitment between the city and the company for the purposes of experimentation.

Perspective to enlarge LEA networks: “beyond Lea's project phases since it follows Lea's guidelines integrating and complementing each other. Since it's open to all schools and stakeholders locally and internationally, an efficient way to disseminate Lea 's principles”.

Viladecans (Spain)

Schools	Students	Teachers	Age range
2	160	5	6-19

Description

In Viladecans, the schools that will be schools labs are 2 public schools, 1 primary and one secondary schools. The schools have participated in a pedagogical and methodological renewal project promoted by the City Council and have received training on how to introduce technology and devices in the teaching-learning process.

Technical equipment available

Classrooms: Digital Smart Board Interactive. Wireless connection.
 Teacher: Laptop. Students: Lenovo Tablet for every student and one digital classroom with 30 laptops in the school

Perspective to enlarge LEA networks: positive "because if an experience is working it's easier to contact with , and therefore to be interested in participating as a follower".

Magdeburg (Germany)

Schools	Students	Teachers	Age range
4	60	8	6-19

Description

The school lab is part of the "Demonstration Centre for IT in Schools Saxony-Anhalt". The centre provides an environment for teachers and principals of all school forms to learn about current trends in IT and concepts to incorporate tools and methods into teaching. Teachers and students can participate in workshops and presentations to try out new ideas. The lab provides a variety of hard- and software for a wide range of activities.

Konnevesi (Finland)

Schools	Students	Teachers	Age range
3	250	40	6-19

Description: The Lapunmäki school consists of three schools: primary, secondary and high school. The students are aged from 6 to 18.

Alltogether there are 250 students. In Konnevesi, every classroom is a school lab. Each classroom is equipped with a big touchscreen TV that can be wirelessly connected to laptops. Every teacher has a laptop for teaching and we use a lot of electronic teaching/learning materials and learning platforms. The Lapunmäki school has 140 Surface 3 laptops and 10 iPads for students, which can be used in class. High school students get their own laptops. The school has a special media room, which includes e.g. a green screen and VR glasses. Four of our classrooms have a lecture recording system for live streaming or HD quality recording. Robotics and programming are a part of education at the Lapunmäki school.

Technical equipment available: Classrooms: 65/82 inch wireless transferable touchscreens, Blackbox Coalesce for wireless connection, Aruba data network. Students: Surface 3, Office 365 (for every students), Ipad, BYOD, Lego Mindstorm robots, BeeBots, Ubtech AlphaPro robots, green screen, vr-goggles, HTC Vive and BlueBots.

Perspective to enlarge LEA networks: We think that the "educational lab" is mainly for the suppliers and schools to develop personal learning environments. To get more LEA followers, we need to enlarge our own networks and draw media attention to LEA.

Braga (Portugal)

Schools	Students	Teachers	Age range
1	20	1	6-19

Description

The LEA School LAB was held at the EB2.3 of Cabreiros / Braga Oeste School Grouping, which is located on the outskirts of the city of Braga.

The activities took place in the ICT room involving the Teacher in charge of ICT and 20 students of the 7th grade. We intend to test the new DISPLAX products at this school and involve Microsoft, namely with its Hands-On Labs and Hacking STEM.

Technical equipment available: ICT classroom with 50m², 25 computers, 1 interactive whiteboard and 1 projector.

Göteborg and Halmstad (Sweden)

Schools	Students	Teachers	Age range
1	30	2	11-19

Description

The LEA school lab was held at the elementary school "Ljungvik" in Lerum, which is one of the municipalities in Göteborgs region. The activities took place in a standard classroom, about 30 students attended and two teachers that was in charge. Each student had a computer each to look at the youtube movies for the project, afterwards the youtube movies was discussed in small groups and then it was discussed in a large group.

Technical equipment available: Computers for each student, projector, smartboard, phones and software, wireless network.

As active member of ENoLL (European Network of Living Labs), the City of Turin had the chance to analysed also cases of study focused on learning technologies which achieved the enrollment on the platform. Two of the most interesting experiences are the Living Labs conducted by the Consortium "Fernando de los Rios" in Andalusia (Spain). The first one, Guadalinfo Living Labs Digital and professional competences for people: Drones and robotic, provided a training for young people and adults to show the process of design, ensembling, code and flight of

technological devices as robots and drones. It bridged the perspective of researchers and users, producing a positive output in terms of new skills and competences.

The second one, Jamtoday Junior: Kids under 13 create videogames based on local history, organized working teams composed by young students to design video games on "Local history". They worked with the assistance of Guadalinfo IT-facilitators, deepening not only the technological aspects, but also the historical ones.

The analysis of other experiences realized by the City of Turin, was revealed essential to structure LEA project and EDULAB call.

3. TORINO CITY LAB

Torino EDULAB is part of a bigger framework, that is Torino City Lab.

Last Autumn the Municipality of Turin launched the Torino City Lab as an initiative-platform aimed at creating simplified conditions for companies interested in conducting tests of solutions for urban living.

With this action, the City officially committed itself to become a promoter of public and private initiatives aimed at improving the urban ecosystem and proposing ideas in different fields of innovation: from IoT (Internet of Things) to collaborative and circular economy activities.

Adopting the perspective of a public actor not only as a regulator, but also as an hub of boost to local development, the Torino City Lab as permanent platform in the urban area was created for social, economic and administrative conditions. First of all, the Lab ensures the access to public spaces through streamlining the administrative process. The initiative is promoted by adopting a new strategy on the part of the local authority, which is capable of acting by making all its sectors work with an integrated perspective. More specifically, the Innovation Area of the

City is committed to working in agreement with the Environment and Green Spaces Area to ensure simplified procedures for experimenters. This cooperative management is born from the desire to quickly coordinate all the local offices and to meet all needs of experimental bodies.

Secondly, the Laboratory is addressed to connect local actors operating in economic sectors considered to be innovative. Through experimentation activities, small and medium-sized companies have the opportunity to create partnerships with large public and private multiutilities that manage the services sector in the area. In addition, the experimenting subjects have the opportunity to deal directly with the world of research. Adopting this approach, a start-up might have the chance to collaborate with big local multiutilities as SMAT (management company of hydric sector), IREN (management company of energy sector), AMIAT (management company of waste) but also with the University and the Politecnico of Turin.

As a third point, the Torino City Lab aims to make it possible to test products and ideas that might be exported on a larger scale. From this point of view, every projects in the Lab are not planned to fill out only local needs, whereas they should be designed to be reused and fitted on wider scales. This designed process is addressed to match the transnational co-creation strategy (Santonen, Creazzo, Griffon, Bòdi, Aversano 2017).

Finally, the Torino City Lab is based on the involvement of citizens as final users and aims to adapt the experimentations to the needs expressed by peoples. Adopting the LEA strategy, this goal will be achieved through adapting the learn technologies to the needs expressed by students and teachers. For this reason, in addition to the permanent chance to propose to the City innovation ideas, the public administration works to

open specific calls based on identified challenges to fill out emerging needs of urban areas or European Union directives.

This last aspect puts the Laboratory in its own right in the category of Living Lab, providing the urban territory to create a public-private-people partnership, achieving the innovation model of the quadruple helix. As described in recent literature, this pattern shapes the collaboration of four main actors: public authorities, industry, academia and citizens (Varmland County Administrative Board 2018).

This platform enables the City to promote new challenges in environmental fields, which are difficult to address with classic regulatory tools, involving a huge variety of public and private actors as well as citizens.

4. CALL EDULAB

The City of Torino has decided to continue working towards the long-term objective set by the LEA, which consists in defining a technological road map by 2030 to improve the European legislation on innovative public procurement in the pre-commercial phase.

Wanting to pursue this goal by putting into practice the testing activity set by the LEA project, the City has decided to plan the Educational Living Lab.

The EDU.LAB starts thanks to a specific call for challenge within the Torino City Lab and aims to create an open space dedicated to educational innovation within the pole of via Bardonecchia 34.

This space will be configured as a place for technical-scientific comparison and experimentation of innovative methodologies and technologies of teaching, development of digital content and the organization of spaces for learning in which comfort, usability, awareness and active role of users are guaranteed. The call aimed at identifying

private subjects (companies) interested in testing - possibly in partnership with other public or private social subjects - will be managed in an open mode of accompanying proposals through the various stages and will last 2 months (approximately from the beginning of April to the beginning of June 2019). Proposals will be examined in order of arrival during the opening period. They will be evaluated by a specific technical committee. This evaluation body will be able to change its composition, involving various services of the city according to the nature of the proposal to ensure a careful assessment.

The proposals will be evaluated according to the five criteria identified within the Torino City Lab platform.

- Innovation - to be evaluated in terms of: degree of originality and potentiality of the solutions proposed with respect to the Italian market of reference". Priority will be given to so-called frontier innovations.
- Technical feasibility - to be assessed in terms of: adequacy of the activities and tools used for testing with respect to the objectives set, the location chosen, timing and budget; compliance with and/or analysis of the regulatory, technical and logistical conditions of the testing context; clarity of the testing proposal, highlighting the "added value" of testing in real conditions", as well as requests for support and facilitation addressed to the City in its various articulations.
- Economic-financial sustainability - to be evaluated in terms of: clarity in identifying a potential reference market; sustainability of the proposed business model.
- Coherence of the proposal to be evaluated in terms of: ability of the project to respond to the sectoral policies of the institution and the guidelines of Torino City Lab.

- Involvement and social and environmental impact to be evaluated in terms of: quality of the analysis methodologies/monitoring tools and evaluation of the social and environmental impact of the experimentation and of the solution to be implemented (KPIs, measurement methods); where relevant, quality of the methodologies used and of the activities planned for the inclusion and participation of relevant territorial actors in the process of co-development for innovation.

4.1. From needs to testing: a call to spread the LEA strategy

To set up the call of the school lab with the intention of responding to the specific needs of students and teachers in the area, it was decided to start from the results of the questionnaire focused on the purpose of new learning technologies (survey described in D3.4).

On the basis of the results, some typical needs of the area to which the call aims to respond have emerged.

Specifically, the first five needs that the technologies could meet are:

- to help students manage their studies
- to help teachers to give students more time to studies
- to help with Science, Math and Technology
- to help students to reach their goals
- to be connected with students (feedback and communication)

4.2. Guidelines to apply Edulab call

Although each context of Learning Technologies' experimentation is different, it may be useful to retrace the strategy adopted by the City of Torino for the design and dissemination of the EDULAB call.

In order to make effective for schools the call of EDULAB, the City of Turin decided to fully adopt the needs and the necessities that emerged during the workshops LEA with students and teachers.

Before the Call publication, the City had started to share and present the aims of EDULAB in other educational projects to increase the interest. Moreover, specific initiatives on Learning Technology Accelerator were organized to explain the potentiality of the educational innovations and understand which kind of outcomes could respond to local needs. This effort allowed to have already at an early stage a large number of schools interested in hosting or participating in the experimentations in Via Bardonecchia.

On the other hand, the City had decided to involve a broad sector of innovative companies in the Call campaign. For this reason EDULAB was presented in several events which hosted private sector committed in topics as social innovation, energy technology and educational activities. This strategy was proved successful not only in encouraging companies to participate, but also in building links of partnership between a wide range of companies. To enhance the new collaborations, the City had organized workshops which had entailed the design of practical experimentations by the participants.

As shown in the attachments, the City launched the call and the request of participation form (Annex 3) on the Torino City Lab site (<https://www.torinocitylab.it/it/>). These actions revealed useful for two main reasons. First of all, the participants could not only gather the form but also have an explanation of the broader framework of the City and download the FAQ to best fit their requests. Furthermore, the inclusion of the call on the broader living lab platform meant that some partners not directly involved in Learning Technologies had the chance to know the project and planning future partnerships.

To evaluate the proposals, a Technical Commission was composed and coordinated by the Educational Services Department, and it was specifically made up of representatives of the City of Turin for areas and sectors of competence. It was conceived as an open and flexible tool on occurrence assisted by external technical-scientific contacts. A heterogeneous committee was considered as the best choice to evaluate proposals for Learning Technology, which had to interact with different administrative areas: from school building to innovation. The evaluation criteria (Annex 4: grid for evaluation), used by the Committee to assess the proposals, were specified in the call (Annex 1) as well as in the application form on the site (Annex 3). This effort was made to help companies in submitting their applications, aiming to EDULAB objectives. In order to better match the expectations of the experimental subjects, as well as to protect the collective interest, the City has decided to adopt a specific Experimentation Agreement (Annex 5). The agreement set out the obligations of the applicants, the commitment of the City as well as the rules regarding the communication of results and intellectual property. In the case of EDULAB, the City decided not to use a managing authority to accompany the experimentation. However, where possible, an authority of experts who knows how to optimize the effort and respond to the requests of the testing companies could prove particularly useful in Living Lab dedicated to Learning Technologies. Specifically, where schools do not have a clear idea of Learning Technologies, this action could be necessary to prepare the context of experimentation.

4.3. Lessons learnt for LEA partners from Edulab call experience

The following paragraph aims to provide a summary of the results of the questionnaire completed by the LEA partners (Annex 6).

The latter consisted of a set of ten open-ended questions to which the participants were able to answer freely.

AN OPEN WINDOW FOR LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES

All the participants meant the LEA living lab both as an effective tool to carry out practical and continuous early market engagement activities, as a way to understand the users needs and acceptability about new learning technologies. On the one hand, participants highlighted needs and opportunities to design market engagement strategies according to the EU laws, regardless of PCP and PPI initiatives. On the other, they claimed the chance to monitor which technologies could fit the users needs, as long as evaluation criteria are established with the companies involved.

NETWORK AND REPLICABILITY

Participants declared that Living Labs on learning technologies enlarged the network of LEA partner. Moreover, they suggested to strengthen links between the local Labs and international partner. This strategy could help to create a bridge from local to global actors involved in learning technologies. Moreover, almost all interviewees thought that the model of Turin could represent a good pattern for future scenarios of innovation and education policies. These policies were meant as tool of permanent educational Living Labs, as long as cities could guarantee sufficient fundings for experimentation. Some of the participants, as Viladecans, aims to enlarge the realized Lab from a single building to the whole urban environment.

ATTRACTIVENESS FOR SCHOOLS

From the questionnaire emerged how educational Labs could be attractive for schools for several reasons. First of all, in those countries/regions/cities/municipalities where digital learning is not used in every schoolday, it could represent an opportunity to enrich and develop the learning. Secondly, the Labs point out which are the actual feelings and needs of user. It represents the only one way to understand how the technologies could help the daily work in schools. To sum up, teachers have the chance to purpose new technique of experimentation which can stimulate the attention and creativity of students.

SUBJECTS OF EXPERIMENTATION

The thoughts about the most effective fields of experimentation for educational Labs are deeply differentiated. Some of the partners sustained the focus have to be specific and not permanent, opening challenges based on specific schools necessity. Others thought that any learning technologies have to be the opportunity to be tested in every moments. Finally, it is emerged the necessity of adopting the technologies in a wider perspective, facing and developing important issues as arts, language and safety.

MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATIVE FRAMEWORK

Several strategies are considered worthy to lead educational Living Labs. Some participants prefer to entrust external experts or universities in the management. Other administrations were directly committed in the communication with companies and schools. However, the key-result on management consists in giving the attention to the users, the students, to achieve the goals. From an administrative perspective, the competition rules should be respected. No discrimination, openness, transparency are considered as general principles. They are considered as benefits

provided by the Public Administration to the involved companies. A call for interest and a selection procedure could not be avoided. For these reasons an open tendering process was the selected tool to guarantee fair criteria of competition.

METHODOLOGICAL STRATEGIES

Interaction with the schools and suppliers was considered important and should take Place from the early start. The direct participations of suppliers at school during the testing activities represented a shared value. Some Municipalities had decided to attend and observe the experimentation to steer in the correct direction every steps.

LEGAL SUGGESTIONS

The testing activities must be conducted following the GDPR regulation (General Data Protection Regulation). This condition made reliable the Living Labs, and it allowed teachers, students and parents to be aware of how their information were shared on the tested platforms. Moreover, it was highlighted as in some cases it could be important a previous approval of other institutions as Ministries of Education.

5. Technical infrastructures needed for an educational living lab

Educational living lab needs to be equipped with contemporary tools, software and furniture. Modern learning space should be equipped with flexible furniture, which can be adapted to different pedagogical scenarios. Such scenarios can be consist of individual, small-group and whole class activities. Walls should be magnetic whiteboards whith possibility to draw and attach materials. In the ideal situation even architectural design reflects ideas of different pedagogical needs.

In the modern educational classroom (educational lab) different user-device ratios should be available: e.g. 1:1 (one device per student); 1:3 (one device per group of three) and 1:all (one device per classroom, e.g. projector). In the age of cheap electronics also 4:1 ratios of devices can be achieved (e.g. Microbit, Arduino, Raspberry hardware). In the modern learning spaces also XR headsets with respective software can be used in teaching and learning, which include tools for augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR) and mixed reality (MR). Modern educational settings also encourage students to produce XR content, which can be created with normal mobile devices or consumer grade 360 cameras and similar equipment

AV-technology is crucial enabler for learning and teaching activities. Screens, projectors and other a/v-equipment should be designed so, that individuals and groups can share their work easily or use secondary/tertiary displays for group work or other activities. In practise, this does mean that in addition to “teachers’s screen” classroom should have also additional displays, screens or projectors which can be connected to mobile devices, laptops, computers and other devices. If possible, wireless screen sharing (mirroring) should be used to connect presenting device to screen, which will replace cabled connectivity in the near future anyway.

Because of the collaboration between different national and international bodies and distance learning is nowadays increasingly popular, conference microphone/speaker and webcam are necessary if not possible to equip laboratory with even more professional audio system.

Current trends include also different tools and materials for STEAM activities in the form of digital fabrication and maker's activities, where some of the materials are very affordable (cardboard, tape etc and arduino or microbit electronic boards), but some devices can be costly like vinyl cutter, 3D printer and laser cutter. STEAM topics can be also learnt via robotics and programming, and there are a lot of different kind of extensions for electronic boards (e.g. Arduino, Microbit) which can be used for learning robotics, electronics etc.

5.1. **Tecnical infrastructures and furnishings of EDULAB in Torino**

The aim of Edulab in Torino is to be an open window on innovation and host periodically tests on innovation technologies about education. Then the space has to be flexible to new test proposals by suppliers, it need to have tecnologica infrastrures and void spaces but also spaces with furnishing to do manual activities.

The EDULAB is inside a middle school (11-14 years old students) at the second floor. It is composed by 450 square meters (in green in the picture).

The EDULAB is composed by 4 rooms with different vocations.

The first is the manual lab where it will be possible to do labs using different materials and technologies but the priority will be the physical construction.

An other room is the library that will be a place where it will be a leisure experience enter and stay for a reading, not oly to find books. It will be connected with the library network of the city, to be open also to the district in afternoon, when the school is closed. One of the aim of EDULAB is to be an open space for the district, associations and citizens.

The computer room will be organized in islands that will have at the center electrical connection. Students will work around islands with circular modular height-adjustable desks.

The last space is composed by two classroom united: there is a zone suitable for frontal lesson with white interactive board but also for cooperative learning with modular desks. In all EDULAB will be WIFI and and in each rooms will be a video projectiong system provided by Cisco.

5.2. The partner network of Torino City Lab

Last Autumn, the City launched the Torino City Lab (TCL) as a platform open to host experimentations of technologies and innovative ideas in the urban public spaces.

First of all, the Lab ensures the access to public spaces through streamlining the administrative process. The initiative is promoted by adopting a new strategy on the part of the local authority, which is capable of acting by making all its sectors work with an integrated perspective. This cooperative management is born from the desire to quickly coordinate all the local offices and to meet all needs of experimental bodies. Secondly, the Laboratory is addressed to connect local actors operating in economic sectors considered to be innovative. Through experimentation activities, small and medium-sized companies have the opportunity to create partnerships with large public and private multiutilities that manage the services sector in the area. In addition, the experimenting subjects have the opportunity to deal directly with the world of research. As a third point, the Torino City Lab aims to make it possible to test products and ideas that might be exported on a larger scale. From this point of view, every project in the Lab are not planned to fill out only local needs, whereas they should be designed to be reused and fitted on wider scales. This designed process is addressed to match the transnational co-creation strategy. Finally, the Torino City Lab is based on the involvement of citizens as final users and aims to adapt the experimentations to the needs expressed by peoples. For this reason, in addition to the permanent chance to propose to the City innovation ideas, the public administration works to open specific calls based on identified challenges to fill out emerging needs of urban

areas or European Union directives. This last aspect puts the Laboratory in its own right in the category of Living Lab, providing the urban territory to create a public-private-people partnership, achieving the innovation model of the quadruple helix.

This platform enables the City to promote new challenges in several fields, which are difficult to address with classic regulatory tools, involving a huge variety of public and private partners as well as citizens.

Learning technologies represent one of the main field of interest for the innovation policies fostered by TCL. For this reason, the City of Turin has decided to involve all of the TCL partners to formulate future policies of educational innovations. Hence, this challenge aims to involve: big companies and international scaling partners to consolidate both the aspects of technology foresight and the diffusion and scalability of the solutions that will be admitted to testing; public utilities, i.e. the subjects that manage public services and assets and that are therefore enabling in some sectors (energy, mobility, water, waste) research institutes and universities private stakeholders co-interested in the activities of experimentation such as development and innovation companies, civil society organizations, etc.

Starting from this network, the City has wanted to face one of the main challenge of the TCL: hosting and improving the Learning technologies. Therefore, in TCL framework the City of Turin has decided to enlarge and enhance partnerships with the most important actors, who are working on spreading and encouraging Learning technologies in schools. This action is being realized through the following steps.

First of all, the City has created a partnership with Nesta Italia foundation, which has recently achieved significant results in terms of analysis of Educational Technologies projects, resumed in the report "[How can we obtain the best from technologies at school?](#)". Nesta is perceived as a

key-actor to deepen past and current experiences of learning technologies in international contexts.

Moreover, the City has designed a specific focus group (according to the LEA project, in parallel with other partners) on learning technologies, to gather all the most meaningful outputs and considerations provided by LEA actors. The focus group has given the opportunity to share doubts and ideas among school officials and teachers. It has entailed the management of discussion offered by Socialfare, one of the TCL partners, which has clearly expressed their commitment in educational and social impact policies. Socialfare represents another actor who will actually play a central role in the coordination and social impact evaluations of EduLab.

As the third point, the City has established a collaboration with Cisco, a companies which will provide technological infrastructures for EduLab. It allows to tailor the spaces to future experimentations.

All of these collaborations are contributing to build EduLab, focusing on transversal competencies offered by partners, and basing on past experiences of Learning technologies application at schools.

LESSONS LEARNED FROM TCL

Although TCL platform exists from almost one year, it has provided useful insights to be reckoned with:

Be open: starting from an open Call for proposal; excluding National constraints; fostering an effective communication campaign on institutional web-sites.

Be compliant: providing equal criteria of participations for the public procurement, guaranteeing equal rights to participating companies and security of end-users.

Be clear: setting out clear rules from the submission, to the evaluation until the experimental phase to monitoring. (See TCL docs: rules of participation, submission form, model contract, monitoring schemes)

Be ready: preparing the lab Space offering minimum technological and furniture requirements

Be participative: trying to involve Technical Partners to Support/animate/evaluate testing activities in your lab in order to raise the value of being involved both for business and for schools

Be engaging within the school community: involving early school managers; training teachers; empowering students; informing families, opening the lab outside the school timeline to other communities

Be measurable: setting out KPIs (Key Performance Indicator) of testing activities, defining monitoring schemes and reporting back to relevant stakeholders.

Be creative: trying to create the best value for all, adapting to upcoming needs of the school community.

According with these suggestions, the City of Turin will implement EduLab to create a direct contact between procurers and end-users. With a long terms perspective, this laboratory could represent the first step to make the schools more creative, more respectful of differences and more open to sharing experinces. Also the intyeration with suppliers could help them to understand better the school system and the procurement in Italy on education technologies.

6. Conclusions

The experience gained through LEA has provided useful suggestions for designing future Living Labs on learning technologies.

First of all, it contributed to define the learning technology environment, sharing several experiences of LL. Every partner had a twofold chance to point out the current learning technologies and to understand the perception of the concept expressed by the users through focus group and questionnaires. They showed that the technologies are not conceived only as the hard ones (Virtual Reality, digital platforms, personal tablets etc.), but also as new methodologies of teaching, more inclusive and proactive.

Secondly, it provided a useful analysis of needs perceived by users. This could be considered both a key-aspect to steer the supply side, and to involve the procurers which could be effectively find a market window in the selected schools.

Moreover, it suggested that there are no methodologies for LL involvement and structure which can be considered effective for every contexts. However, it made it possible to identify the principles of transparency, openness and fairness as the starting points for the selection of procurers.

Specifically, it provided practical sample of tenders and contracts which might a good input for administrations who are going to propose a LL on learning technologies.

Eventually, It made clear all the potentials of technologies in schools, highlighting a new idea of technology based on the sharing of experiences, the creativity and the adaptability to the needs of each individual student or teacher.

According to the results and suggestions provided by LEA experience, (in particular on focus group activity conducted on 14th of October 2019), the City of Turin wants to select an external scientific committee which would play the role of "Management Committee" for the Edulab initiative. This body would provide communication and facilitation strategies to follow the companies (8 proposals of tests arrived), and it

would guarantee activities from 30 months up to 36. Specifically, the Committee would work on the follow fields of action:

- support, management and assessment activities of experimentations. It should work on both the admitted proposals and the future ones.
- planning of the involvement strategy. On the one hand, it should co-design with schools activities and laboratories. On the other, it should spread the EduLab opportunities through the network of schools.
- coordinating activities of local and international partners. They should be aimed at organizing a shared calendar, which should guarantee consistency and continuity of EduLab experimentations.
- constructing a specific offer. It should write an offer which entails all of the class, purposing specific technologies based on the age of students.
- setting of work areas. It should design the spaces of EduLab to effectively host the technologies. Depending on the circumstances, they have to be equipped to accommodate 3D printers, robots and data platforms etc.
- installation of sensors on EduLab building.
- writing a catalogue. The Committee should produce and update a catalogue which points out all of the technologies hosted in EduLab. Moreover, the catalogue should match experimentations to the reference age of the students, to guarantee an optimization of results in terms of users involvement and feedback for the companies.

Annex 1: Call Edulab: rules of participation

Rules of participation and mode of operation of EDULAB

FRAMEWORK OF THE INITIATIVE AND GENERAL OBJECTIVES

According to DGC no. 01591/007 of 07/05/2019, the EDU.LAB - "Educational Living Lab" – is activated in the framework of the initiative "Torino City Lab" (www.torinocitylab.com) aimed at allowing the testing of innovative solutions for urban living in real conditions.

The EDU.LAB will be managed by the Istituzione della Città di Torino ITER (Istituzione Torinese per una Educazione Responsabile) in collaboration with the Divisione Servizi Educativi e il Servizio Innovazione e Fondi europei della Città di Torino.

The initiative is part of the realization of a new Educational Hub that ITER is setting up at the school building located in Via Bardonecchia 34, a project that includes among its actions also the development of a pilot of "Educational Living Lab". An experience of innovation laboratory born in the framework of the European project LEA - "Learning Technologies Accelerator" (www.learntechaccelerator.eu/), in which the City of Torino proposed to develop and model a space dedicated to innovation in the educational field where to allow the testing of solutions for teaching and for the organization of new generation learning environments. An educational environment with adequate equipment to host the testing of innovative methodologies and technologies in the fields of teaching, development of digital content, the organization of spaces dedicated to learning in which comfort, usability, awareness and active role of users are guaranteed. The EDU-LAB will be a space open to technical-scientific comparison and to all schools interested in testing first-hand didactic experiences conducted in an environment conceived in an innovative way. Experimentation will be conducted by experts by engaging active roles to students and teachers. According to the logic of "living lab", the different experiences will contribute to improve and make more effective the methodologies and solutions proposed, also thanks to the active role of the users themselves involved as effective drivers of change. At the same time, educators, pedagogues, researchers, companies and designers will be able to experiment methods, solutions or products, monitoring and evaluating the results of the tests carried out with the interaction of their users of reference. In this perspective, the City of Torino, through the Educational Living Lab of Torino City Lab, aims to:

- contribute to the development of the innovation market in the field of learning technologies;
- test technologies to encourage innovative teaching methods in schools, combining an inclusive approach that takes into account the needs of each student and that, even with the use of digital tools, increases the ability to respond to problems of 1 different kinds and promotes teamwork;
- encourage the application of Internet of Things-enabled solutions to promote policies and services, but also data-driven educational pathways related to school and neighbourhood metabolism;

- promote the reconversion of school structures through a rethinking of spaces, which is functional to the development of new learning methodologies and the development of solutions for comfort and usability;
- enhance teachers' skills to support more effective development of new technologies;
- create a network open to all schools interested in participating in workshops dedicated to new learning technologies and the exchange of skills and experience;
- experiment with forms of connection between education systems and territorial structures dedicated to culture and education (museums, technological centres, etc.)
- strengthen the opportunities of relationship between schools and territory in a logic of "school civic centre".
-

THE VALUE PROPOSAL: SUPPORT TO TESTING AND AGEVOLATIONS

The City of Torino, through ITER (Istituzione Torinese per una Educazione Responsabile) will offer a constant support in order to favour the access and to facilitate the conduction of the experimentations. The offices of the Innovation Service and European Funds will support the initiative in the initial investigation phase as well as for communication activities on the portal www.torinocitylab.com.

The City undertakes to support the proposed experimentations through the activation of all the authorization or enabling procedures within its competence as well as through a liaison activity with the companies that are interested in, or that can be involved for this purpose, and with the other partners of Torino City Lab. Specifically, the City of Torino undertakes to support, with a free of charge contribute, the activities of communication and dissemination of the experimentation through its institutional channels and the creation of a section dedicated to the results of the Notice within the Torino City Lab website. It is specified, however, that where, during the experimentation, data or notices are produced regarding situations that affect citizenship, the City does not undertake to activate any specific action: the information and results produced in this phase will in fact be used by the City only for study and analysis purposes for the purposes of this initiative. No financial resources are foreseen for the testing by the City.

WHO CAN PARTICIPATE

The subjects admitted are Enterprises, including Social Enterprises, in individual and collective shape (joint-stock companies, partnerships, Cooperative societies), with registered offices in Italy or abroad.

Other subjects from the world of research or other realities (e.g. public and private bodies, including associations) are also admitted, but only if in partnership with a company. In the case of partnerships, all subjects must fill in the Participation Application and identify the lead partner who will be the only representative of the Administration for the fulfilment of all contractual obligations.

All subjects must meet the legal requirements to contract with the Public Administration pursuant to art. 80 of Legislative Decree no. 50/2016.

OBJECT OF EXPERIMENTATION

This call for proposals shall be considered open to experimentations of:

- a) innovative technologies applied to teaching: proposals may concern both innovations in the use of instruments already present in the institutions and focus on new technological material. Each proposal must include a plan for training and discussion with teachers in order to be exploited to the full.
- b) new ways of thinking about the indoor and outdoor school space: for example, through furniture, fittings, sensors, technologies or innovative solutions for comfort, solutions based on nature (nature-based and green solutions, integrated concepts, etc.. The proposals can be dedicated to the reorganization of learning environments, both indoor and outdoor, with an inclusive perspective, which ensures indoor comfort, energy-environmental sustainability and promotes teamwork or individual facilitating the usability of new technologies.
- c) new pedagogical, didactic and formative approaches: the proposals can be oriented on the experimentation of new learning methodologies, training modules, laboratory activities or innovative contents, which are a stimulus for students to actively participate by offering them the opportunity to experiment with new environments, freely express themselves and share their knowledge and creativity.

ASSET AND AREA OF EXPERIMENTATION

In addition to the availability of the spaces placed in the complex of Via Bardonecchia, according to the evaluation of the City, some experiments may be hosted in other schools in the city. It will be possible to view the spaces made available in a day of open day specially organized.

TIME OF TESTING

The duration of the experimentation will be proposed by the proposing parties according to the type and complexity of the activities planned. Anyway, the maximum duration is 12 months. It is recommended to focus the part testing application with users during the school year (September-June).

WAYS OF PARTICIPATION

Experimentation proposals have to be submitted online through direct application on the project's website (www.torinocitylab.com). The City of Torino will offer information and support to the drafting of the application through online and offline activities.

TIMING AND METHODS OF EVALUATION

This Notice shall be valid for 60 days from the date of its publication. Therefore, It will be open from 27 May to 26 July 2019.

The submission of proposals for experimentation may take place until the closing date of the call, scheduled for 16:00 on 26 July 2019.

The administration reserves the right to reopen the application window on the basis of the proposals received and the availability of space.

The proposals received will immediately be subject to an admissibility assessment by the offices of the Innovation and European Funds Service in conjunction with ITER.

They will then be subject to a merit assessment by a "Technical Commission" coordinated by the Educational Services Department, specifically made up of representatives of the City of Turin for areas and sectors of competence and possibly assisted by external technical-scientific contacts.

According to the availability of the Administration, It will be possible to set up hearings with the proposers of the individual projects during this phase.

The Commission will proceed to the examination of the project proposal and will provide the outcome of the evaluation activities within 60 days, except in cases of force majeure due to the complexity of the projects and the necessary involvement of third parties with respect to the Administration and the partners of Torino City Lab.

As a result of the evaluation, a "Partnership Agreement" will be signed which will specify the reciprocal commitments and interests and which will start the "testing", starting from its operational design and the relative authorization process.

The total duration of any authorization process can be quantified as a maximum of a further 45 days.

The Administration has the right to carry out evaluation activities on a regular basis according to the number of proposals received: by way of example, the evaluation window may be temporarily closed upon receipt of a given number of proposals (for example 10), in order to allow adequate evaluation activities. The City reserves the right to bring forward the closing date of the call in case the number of proposals is high. Subsequently, the appraisal and evaluation activities will proceed on a regular basis.

AVAILABILITY OF DATA

The City of Torino, also through the own partnership, will make available useful data for the purposes of the experiments. This support activity will start from what is already available on the open data platform (<http://aperto.comune.torino.it/>). Similarly, the subjects admitted to the testing undertake to agree with the City the modalities of consultation of the data (if any) produced within the scope of the experimentation in real time, as well as the type of data, the modalities of release (also, in part, in "open" format, where possible and relevant) and the frequency with which these must be made available on platforms or management systems used by the City. Where the activity of collaboration is relevant from the point of view of the processing of personal data, the Parties will regulate the processing in full compliance with the applicable rules including the EU Regulation 679/2016 (General Data Protection Regulation).

Any detailed aspects will be governed by the "Experimentation Contract".

EVALUATION CRITERIA

Proposals will be evaluated on the basis of the following criteria with the purpose of drawing up the ranking of projects received:

- level of innovation - to be evaluated in terms of: degree of originality and potentiality of the solutions proposed relatively to the Italian market of reference". Priority will be given to so-called "frontier innovations".
- technical feasibility - to be evaluated in terms of: adequacy of activities and tools used for testing relatively to the planned objectives, the selected contexts, time and budget; compliance with and/or analysis of the regulatory, technical and logistical conditions of the testing context; clearness of the testing proposal, highlighting the "added value" of testing in real conditions", as well as requests for support and facilitation addressed to the City in its different articulations.
- economic-financial sustainability - to be evaluated in terms of: clearness in identifying a potential reference market; sustainability of the proposed business model.
- coherence of the proposal to be evaluated in terms of: ability of the project to respond to the sectoral policies of the institution and the guidelines of Torino City Lab.
- involvement and social and environmental impact to be evaluated in terms of: quality of the analysis methodologies/monitoring tools and evaluation of the social and environmental impact of the experimentation and of the solution to be implemented (KPIs, measurement methods); if it is considered as a significant aspect of the purpose, the quality of the used methodologies to manage the activities of inclusion and participation of relevant territorial actors in the process of co-development for innovation and the design of the evaluation phase.

On the basis of these criteria, a specific ranking will be drawn up and a limited number of proposals will be selected for testing. As long as financial resources are made available and in connection to the areas of development of interest for City and the partners, financial facilitation for testing may be set up.

Annex 2: Call Edulab: request of participation

REQUEST OF PARTICIPATION

**APPLICATION
"EXPRESSION OF INTEREST"**

To the City of Turin
Educational Service Division
Via Bazzi 4
10152 TORINO

The undersigned

Surname and name _____
 Born in the _____
 resident in the Municipality of _____
 Province _____ Street / Square _____
 As _____
 authorized to legally represent _____
 based in the Municipality of _____ CAP _____
 Province _____ Street / Square _____
 CF _____ PIVA _____
 Tel. _____ fax _____ e-mail _____

aware of the penal sanctions foreseen in case of untruthful declarations and falsehoods, art. 76 of the Presidential Decree of 28 December 2000, n. 445 and the consequent loss of the benefits linked to art. 75 of the aforementioned decree,

DECLARES THAT

- The proponent is in possession of the requisites prescribed by law for admission to public contributions or similar benefits .
- The legal representative of the organization is in full enjoyment of the civil and political rights.
- The legal representative of the organization has not been convicted with a final sentence or criminal decree of irrevocable sentence or sentence of application of the penalty on request pursuant to Article 444 of the Code of Criminal Procedure for one of the offenses provided for by art. 80 of Legislative Decree 50/2016.
- The proponent is not in any debt situation towards the City of Turin.
- The proponent is not identifiable as "company in difficulty" pursuant to art. 2 paragraph 18 of EU Regulation 651/2014.

- The proponent is in order - where relevant - with the provisions in force concerning the building and urban planning regulations, work regulations, accident prevention and environmental protection and/or to commit to their respect also in relation to the activities carried out in the operational offices.

ALSO DECLARE

- to fully accept the contents of the "Conditions of participation of EDULAB".
- to act in compliance with the principles of good faith, professional correctness, loyalty towards the Municipality of Turin and the other participants of TorinoCityLab
- to be registered as a follower of the LEA project at: <https://www.learntechaccelerator.eu/followlea>
- where needed, to be part of the partnership whose lead partner, only interlocutor of the Administration for the fulfillment of all contractual obligations, will be:

According to the Presidential Decree of 28 December 2000, n. 445 and subsequent amendments on the subject of substitutive declarations, the City of Turin is required to carry out, on a sample basis, checks on the substitutive declarations.

PRESENTS ITS FORMAL EXHIBITION OF INTEREST

to participate in this Torino City Lab Challenge.

Date_____ Signature of the Legal Representative_____

Where the collaboration between XXXX and the Municipality of Turin detects from the point of view of the processing of personal data, the Parties will regulate the processing in full compliance with the applicable rules including the EU Reg. 679/2016 (General Data Protection Regulation).

(date)

(readable signature)

Pursuant to and for the purposes of Article 1341 of the Civil Code, we hereby expressly approve the above mentioned.

(date)

(readable signature)

Annex 3: Call Edulab: questions for the form on line

I) GENERAL INFO	
(*) Company:	
(*) Address:	
(*) Legal Representative:	
(*) Proposal Title:	
(*) Project Main Contact	
(*) Contact telephone:	
(*) Contact e-mail:	
II) PROPOSAL DESCRIPTION	
(*) Brief description of the Solution:	(Max 1.500 characters)
(*) Brief description of the Company:	(max 100 characters)
(*) Main type of technology:	
	SOFTWARE
	HARWARE
	INDOOR
	OUTDOOR
	OTHER
(*) Detailed Use case description	(Max. 5.000 characters)
(*) Coherence with local, national, european sectoral policies & initiatives:	(Max 2.000 characters)
(*) Current Type and Level of Involvement of final users/communities	(Max 2.000 characters)
(*) Estimated duration:	
Partners:	Nr.
If Yes, specify here	Name
III) TESTING FACILITIES REQUESTED	
Justify the need of testing in real conditions:*	
Detailed Plan of Testing activities (Objective, Activities, Timeline)	
(*) Area involved (classroom, courtyard, etc):	CLASSROOM
	COURTYARD
	OTHER
Give detail of the the area eventually needed (dimension, type of installation)	
Requested Support for Technical infrastructure: (power supply, connectivity, interactive whiteboard, mobile devices, other)	
(*) Other Specific requests for City of Turin	
V) INNOVATIVENESS OF THE SOLUTION	

Type of Innovation (*)	Product
	Service
	Process
	Mix
(*) Brief explanation of the innovativeness compared to the Italian state of the art (including non technology innovativeness)	Max 3.000 characters
VI) ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY	
Budget of testing	Euros
Proposed Business model	Max 2.000 characters
VII) IMPACT	
(*)Specify "Technical" KPIs	
<i>Within the Testing period</i>	
<i>Beyond the Testing Period</i>	
(*)Specify "Socio-economical" KPIs	
<i>Within the Testing period</i>	
<i>Beyond the Testing Period</i>	
VII) ATTACHMENTS:	
*Request of participation duly signed	Insert here
*ID Card or similar for the Leagal representative	Insert here
*3 slides describing the proposal	Insert here
Further Technical Documents to best explain the solutions: e.g. Analytical Description the solutions, including Use case; Timeline, including milestones; Business Model Canvas; Plans and maps.	Max XX MG

Annex 4: Call Edulab: grid for evaluation

CRITERION	Evaluation scheme
CONSISTENCY	<i>To be evaluated in terms of: the degree of consistency of the proposal with respect to the scope of activity of Torino City Lab and the administrative competencies and sectoral policies of the institution.</i>
	YES
	NO
FEASIBILITY	<i>to be evaluated in terms of: adequacy of the activities and tools used for testing with respect to the objectives set, the location chosen, the timing and the budget; respect and / or analysis of the regulatory, technical and logistical conditions of the experimental context; clarity of the testing proposal, giving evidence of the "added value" of testing in real conditions ", as well as requests for support and facilitation aimed at the City in its various articulations</i>
0	Insufficient
1	Low
2	Sufficient
3	Good
4	optimal
5	excellent
INNOVATIVE	<i>to be evaluated in terms of: degree of originality and potential of the solutions proposed with respect to the European reference market ". Priority will be given to frontier innovations.</i>
0	Insufficient
1	Low
2	Sufficient
3	Good
4	optimal
5	excellent
ECONOMIC AND FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY	<i>to be evaluated in terms of: clarity in identifying a potential reference market; sustainability of the proposed business model</i>
0	Insufficient
1	Low
2	Sufficient
3	Good
4	optimal
5	excellent

INVOLVEMENT AND SOCIAL IMPACT	<i>to be evaluated in terms of: quality of the analysis methodologies / tools for monitoring and social evaluation of the experimentation and of the solution at regime (KPIs, measurement method); where relevant, the quality of the methodologies used and the activities planned for the inclusion and participation of relevant territorial actors in the process of co-development for innovation</i>
0	Insufficient
1	Low
2	Sufficient
3	Good
4	optimal
5	excellent
Score for admission to testing	The criterion on coherence is exclusive and is expressed in YES or NO. No criterion must have insufficient evaluation Score of at least 12/20

Annex 5: Call Edulab: agreement

(MODEL) EXPERIMENTATION AGREEMENT

Between

- **CITTÀ DI TORINO**, located in Turin, Piazza Palazzo di Città 1 and domiciled here for the purpose of this agreement, here represented by XXXXXX as XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX (hereinafter, for brevity, even just "City")

IS

- **XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX** established in XXXXXXXXXXXXXXX and domiciled herein for the purposes of this agreement, here represented by XXXXXXXXXXX as legal representative (hereinafter, for the sake of brevity, even only "Proponent")

The City of Turin and XXXXXXXXXXXXXXX are hereinafter also referred to, separately, "Part" and jointly, "Parties"

GIVEN THAT:

- As part of the **TORINO CITY LAB** initiative promoted by the City of Turin with DGC. mech. 2018 XXXXX / 068 del XXXXX, XXXXX (Applicant Name) has regularly submitted an application registered with num. prot. XX of XXXXX 2017.
- In particular, the testing proposal concerns the implementation of (*max two lines*)
- This proposal was declared admissible under the "Rules of operation" as attested in the management decision of the XXXXXXX, num. mech. XXXXXXX.
- For the purposes of the evaluation, the proposal was analyzed by a duly constituted Technical Committee, which met on XXXXXXX.
- According to the results of the aforementioned evaluation committee, approved with managerial determination num. mech. XXXXXXX, the Proponent's proposal has been approved.

All of this premised,

AGREE AS FOLLOWS

Art. 1 - REFERENCE TO THE PREMISES

The premises form an integral and substantial part of this act and as such the parties ratify them.

Art. 2 - SUBJECT

The object of the experimentation is XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX *
(* insert description of the experimentation, with indication of the proposed solution and in-depth analysis on the characteristics of the technology and on the requests for facilitation to the institution The description can include an initial phase of operational planning It is possible to refer to a detailed technical annex Attachment 1).

The activity also provides for the identification of key indicators for the assessment of the impact of the specific experimentation, which will be defined within the first quarter after the start of the experimentation. These indicators can be modified / integrated during the experimentation.

Art. 3 - DURATION

The duration of the trial is XX months, starting from the signing of the agreement. The detailed time schedule of the testing activities is shown in the annex to this Agreement (Annex 2).

The present Agreement is productive of effects from the moment of its subscription for all the preparatory activities and until the end of the experimentation as specified above.

The Municipal Administration reserves the right to grant an extension of the duration of the trial after its conclusion, by means of an adequately motivated letter exchange between the parties.

Art. 4 - EXPERIMENTATION AREA

If a physical installation is planned, please specify its location or the area covered by the planned intervention. If the definition of the area is part of the initial design phase, it is possible, however, to request a rough project of the area concerned and / or the estimated area of coverage, reporting the whole graphically in Annex 3.

The attached project will be modifiable within the first trimester from the start of the experimentation, also on the basis of subsequent comparisons with the City's concerned Departments.

Art. 5 PARTNERSHIP (if necessary)

The present experimentation will be carried out within a partnership consisting of the following subjects:

1. XXX (proposer)
2. XXXX
3. XXXXXXXXXXXX.

The partners of this proposal contribute to the implementation of the same in the measure agreed with the proposer, who acts as coordinator and responsible for relations with the City of Turin.

The proponent defines the modalities of management of the proposal and of joint responsibility between partners through ad hoc agreements.

Art. 6 DISCIPLINE OF USE OF PUBLIC SOIL *(if necessary)*

Where necessary for the purposes of the experimentation referred to in this agreement, the City of Turin will forward an authorization request for the occupation of public land for "Events and Events" or "Building Works" pursuant to the COSAP Regulation. Employment Tax Spaces and Public Areas .

The concession relating to this initiative is excluded from the application of the occupancy fee pursuant to art. 14, paragraph 1, letter a) of the COSAP Regulation and therefore the organizers will have to pay only the expected secretarial costs to the City. These exemptions, and the relative lack of income for the City, have been approved by Deliberazione di Giunta Comunale nmecc XXXXXXXX of XXXXX and Determine resolved by the Board and reported in the relative management directives approving the testing contracts.

All obligations and charges deriving from the granting of the use of public land for the purposes and for the duration of the present experimentation are the responsibility of the proponent, who is therefore bound to respect the laws, regulations and provisions that govern the subject.

The authorization is not to be considered a substitute for the possibly necessary "Ordinance of the City Traffic and Traffic Sector" or any other mandatory authorization for the type of activity related to employment.

Any commercial activities on public land must be previously authorized by the competent sector.

As better specified in the following article 6, they will be the sole responsibility of the proposer:

- the expenses deriving from the restoration of any damage caused to the public land, as established by the City;
- the costs of cleaning the ground deriving from the eventual extraordinary intervention of AMIAT caused by the occupation.

The proponent will have to maintain a conduct that is not an obstacle or a danger to pedestrian and vehicular traffic and that does not cause disturbance to public peace nor danger to public safety; the aeration grids present must not be affected.

The concession will be revoked in the case of ascertained violations, ascertained abuses committed in direct connection with the occupation and its purposes, violation of specific legal and / or regulatory provisions as well as for the occurrence of any situation deemed unfavorable according to the justified judgment of the city. Pursuant to art. 23 of the COSAP regulation a representative of the proponent must always be readily available during the experimentation.

Art. 7 OBLIGATIONS OF THE PROPOSER (not all the obligations mentioned are of relevance - it is possible to select only those that are consistent with the type of experimentation envisaged)

The proponent undertakes to carry out what described in article 2 and better specified in the annexes, without producing any cost or charge to the City of Turin.

The main obligations for the proposer are detailed below:

t) Environmental sustainability

The proponent undertakes, in the context of experimentation, to implement actions and measures aimed at full protection of environmental sustainability, with the adoption of ecologically and socially sustainable behaviors .

b) Installation, realization of experimentation and maintenance

All activities and related expenses related to the installation, construction and maintenance of any systems / services / solutions considered an integral part of the experimentation and for the entire duration of the same are the responsibility of the proposer. Nothing is due from the Public Administration.

c) Data sharing

The proposer undertakes to agree with the City on how to consult the data produced in real time, as well as the type of data, the modalities of release (also, in part, in "open" format where possible and relevant) and the frequency with these must be made available on platforms or management systems used by the organization.

d) Connection to the network and users

The connections to the electricity, gas or water network will be managed directly by the proposer in relation with the subsidiaries of reference or other subjects held liable. The costs of connection and future users will be borne by the proponents for the duration of the experimentation, unless otherwise prescribed. The timing of activation will depend on the complexity of the proposed intervention.

is) Cleaning

If the experimental conditions imply a significant variation in the disposition of public areas and objects such as to imply the impossibility on the part of the manager of the public cleaning service and waste collection or significant additional costs, the realization and the resulting cleaning costs of the testing area is intended to be borne by the user.

f) Post-experimentation restoration

All the activities and related expenses related to the restoration of the situation in question, including dismantling, maintenance of the testing area (if necessary) and disposal, are the responsibility of the proposer.

g) Advertising installations

For the installation of advertising installations of a temporary nature in the testing area, the Proponent is also responsible for the payment of the fee for advertising initiatives (CIMP) as established by the current "Regulations for the application of the fee for advertising initiatives" no. 335. This fee may be reduced to 50% within the limits set by art. 22 of the aforementioned regulation only if connected to the activities carried out in collaboration with the City of Turin in the context of this initiative.

h) Liability for damages to things or people

The proponent is attributed to all responsibilities provided by law regarding the carrying out of activities and interventions included in the experimentation.

The proponent is therefore obliged to answer for all the damages attributable to activities carried out during the experimentation which, due to construction defect or incorrect operation of the interventions, may derive from buildings and plants, to means of work, to people and things, for any reason present in the area where the intervention is carried out or in its surroundings.

The proponent undertakes in such cases to hold the City of Turin unharmed from any request for compensation. The proponent can, for his own protection, take out an adequate insurance policy to cover any damage caused during the experimentation.

Where relevant, the proposer may also regulate with third parties access to services or utilities object of the experimentation through declaration of exclusion of responsibility or similar instruments in accordance with the regulations in force.

In order to correctly monitor itinere, the proponent undertakes to provide the City of Torino with periodic updates on the progress of the experimentation and to promptly report any critical issues that may jeopardize the correct execution of the activities being tested and compliance with the agreed time schedule.

The proponent undertakes to provide the City of Turin with data and information useful for assessing the impacts of the trials (key indicators) and for the analysis of the post-intervention scenarios.

Art. 8 COMMITMENTS OF THE CITY *

The City undertakes to support the testing by the proposer through the activation of all the authorizing or enforcing procedures for which it is responsible, as well as

through a liaison with the participating companies involved or involved and with the other partners of Turin. City Lab.

(Possible to specify here the contribution possibly provided by other partners of Torino City Lab and that will be able to become signatory of the agreement for this purpose)*

The City of Turin undertakes, in particular, to support, free of charge, the communication and dissemination activities of the experimentation through its institutional channels and the creation of a section dedicated to the results of the Notice within the Torino City Lab website (under construction).

It is specified, however, that where, during the experimentation, data or warnings are produced concerning situations that affect citizenship, the City does not undertake to activate any specific action: the information and results produced in this phase will in fact be used by the City only for reasons of study and analysis for the purposes of this initiative.

Art. 9 PROVISIONS ON THE PUBLICITY OF THE INITIATIVE AND USE OF THE CITY LOGOS

Participants are allowed to use the logo of the City of Turin and Torino City Lab to publicize the experimentation after verification with the Special Innovation Project, European Funds and Smart City in compliance with the municipal regulation n. 373, recognizing the patronage of the City.

Art. 10 DISCIPLINE ON COMMUNICATION OF ENVIRONMENTAL DATA TO CITIZENSHIP (only if relevant)

Where the results of the experimentation consist wholly or in part in the monitoring of environmental parameters having a high impact on the quality of life of citizens and in the subsequent communication of such data to the public, the proposer is obliged to agree the methods of public dissemination with the City.

In particular, with specific regard to sensitive environmental data such as those relating to air quality, the proponent will comply with the obligations provided for by Legislative Decree 13 August 2010, n.155 "Implementation of Directive 2008/50 / EC on quality ambient air and for cleaner air in Europe "and its modifications.

In the communication to the outside of the environmental data collected during the experimentation, the proposer must follow the following provisions:

- the proposer must declare that the results of the measures taken are not to be considered official data of the City or by other competent bodies, such as in particular ARPA Piemonte, with reference to art. 18 of Legislative Decree n.155 / 2010;
- quantitative data cannot be disseminated publicly;

- the qualitative data can be shared on platforms or mobile applications to a limited number of users who will access the service through access credentials for the trial period.

In any case, the City is not responsible for the given product and will not follow up on any positive action in direct response to the phenomena documented in the context of the experimentation.

Art. 11 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

Where relevant, the intellectual property rights that may emerge from the testing activities covered by this Agreement and the possibility of exploitation arising therefrom are generally understood by the proposer.

In this case, the proponent is therefore obliged to indemnify and keep the City of Torino unharmed from all claims, responsibilities, losses and damages claimed by any interested party, even if the proponent uses devices and solutions techniques that others have already obtained the right to.

During the operational phase, XXXX the City of Turin will regulate, where necessary, the regime of detail applicable in terms of intellectual property in specific agreements.

Art. 12 RESOLUTION

The Agreement is considered terminated if the trial is not activated within 60 days of the signing of this Agreement. Any unforeseen or unforeseeable external event that does not allow the start of the experimentation in the agreed times may also be the cause of termination of the Agreement.

Art. 13 CONCLUSION OF THE EXPERIMENTATION

At the conclusion of the activities, all the costs associated with restoring the situation in question are to be borne by the proposer, including dismantling, maintenance of the impacted areas and disposal of objects and waste in compliance with current regulations.

The City of Turin reserves the right to agree with the proponent any scenarios of post-intervention use that will be the subject of subsequent agreements, in any case without charges for the City.

With this proceeding, the Municipality does not undertake to purchase any product that is the object of the experimentation.

If the Municipality of Turin intends in the future to purchase similar products to one of those tested, the Authority will observe the current regulations governing the acquisition of goods and services of the Public Administrations.

Art. 14 DISPUTES

For any disputes arising in connection with the interpretation, execution and / or application of this Agreement, or in any case indirectly connected to it, which can not be defined in an amicable manner, the Court of Turin has exclusive jurisdiction.

WWW.TORINOCITYLAB.COM

Corso Ferrucci 122, 10141, Torino

Art. 15 PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA

Where the collaboration between XXXX and the Municipality of Turin detects from the point of view of the processing of personal data (for example XXXX) the Parties will regulate the processing in full compliance with the applicable rules including the EU Regulation 679/2016 (General Data Protection Regulation).

In the case of video surveillance and / or video shootings for dissemination and study purposes as part of the experimentation, the proposer is obliged to affix information to citizens who pass through the monitored areas and to signal the collection of data. The information can be prepared according to the model developed by the Authority for the Protection of Personal Data and must be clearly visible, as well as indicating who performs the detection of images and for what purposes. The aims and methods of carrying out these activities must in any case be carried out in compliance with the applicable sector regulations

Art. 16 TAXES, TAXES AND ADDITIONAL EXPENSES

All additional expenses, taxes and fees that may be generated for the execution of the trial are to be understood by the proposer.

Art. 17 GENERAL PROVISIONS

For anything not provided for by the present Agreement, reference is made to the laws, regulations and regulations in force.

Read, approved and undersigned

Turin, there ...

THE COMPANY

THE MUNICIPALITY OF TURIN

WWW.TORINOCITYLAB.COM

Corso Ferrucci 122, 10141, Torino

Annex 6: Lesson learnt questionnaire

Name of procurer/partner you represent	Can the "Educational lab" be used to carry out practical and continuous early market engagement activities, as a permanent "window" on the Learntech market to be used by schools and public authorities, to qualify their innovation demand, even if not directly linked to the LEA PPI/PCP?	Can we think about it as a way to constantly monitor users need and acceptability/effectiveness of technology? (motivate your answer please)	Can the "educational lab" be a smart way to enlarge the LEA follower networks? (motivate your answer please)
Municipality of Konnevesi	Yes	Yes, as long as it is negotiated with the local schools / municipalities.	We think that the "educational lab" is mainly for the suppliers and schools to develop personal learning environments. To get more LEA followers, we need to enlarge our own networks and draw media attention to LEA.
SBE (Sara Bedin)	For sure as a permanent window on the Learntech market. The market engagement activity shouldn't interfere with the competition and should be designed according to the EU competition law (with or without PCP/PPI initiatives). The qualification of the (public) demand should be based on internal assessment.	Yes, the acceptability and effectiveness of a technology are very valid objectives, involving users. The value of Edu Lab is the involvement of the users (more than the industries). The industry engagement is functional, not the main result.	Yes, of course.
Viladecans City Council	Yes	Yes, in case it has been previously defined for this objective in the technological agreement with companies in charge of.	Yes, because if a experience is working it's easier to contact with , and therefore to be interested in participating as a follower.
RSA (Ministerium der Finanzen des Landes Sachsen-Anhalt)	Yes	Monitoring of users needs and acceptance would be possible during certain events with additional resources. The lab provides the framework for this kind of monitoring.	In general, the lab can be used for LEA events and LEA can be promoted in the lab.
Halmstad	Yes	Yes, but not to the extent Turino has since we have school lab that is school led.	Not the kind of school lab we have in Halmstad.

Name of procurer/partner	Do you think it could be possible to replicate the	Do you think the "educational lab" could be	Which is or how you imagine could	How is actually managed or how do
--------------------------	--	---	-----------------------------------	-----------------------------------

Partner you represent	Torino permanent "educational lab" model in your countries?	useful and attractive for schools? Why?	be the main sectoral focus of your school lab?	you propose to manage the School Lab?
Municipality of Konnevesi	Yes.	Yes. Especially in those countries/regions/cities/municipalities where digital learning isn't used in every schoolday, it could attract students to choose a school with educational labs.	Any learntech	School –led
SBE (Sara Bedin)	Not applicable. Yes	Yes, budget restrictions obstacle innovation adoption. Very valid to enable rational investments evaluation and share experiences, reducing barriers in the adoption of the innovation.	Not a permanent focus, but clear and specific focus on any tech related to school (not exclusively learntech, but also management, safety, lay-out)	Need to contextualize the lab in a very real context. The value is the involvement of the users!
Viladecans City Council	Yes. Viladecans City Council is currently projecting a new public library focused in science, where is planned to have a city lab. Innovation and education are priorities in our city strategy and we have legal competences, so we hope it will be achieved in 2020.	Yes, because It will be the way to be in touch with innovation, where teachers and students can have singular experiences with innovative ITC.		City council leading it with external consultant
RSA (Ministerium der Finanzen des Landes Sachsen-Anhalt)	Some aspects of the Torino model are established in our school lab, too. It is not directly connected to a school, but open for all schools and school representatives, providing a classroom-setting with solutions for infrastructure and digital tools that can be tested.	Schools (teacher, students representatives) can get information about infrastructure and new technology for classroom use, they can test and experiment and then decide what they would like to implement in their own classrooms.	Any learntech	by the university
Halmstad	In bigger cities yes, but not in smaller cities because of financing issues etc.	Yes, because both students and teachers can test new techniques. The question is how to do it when the school lab is school led.	Any learntech	School –led

Name of partner	Have you already	Can you list any user	Do you see any legal constraints for
<p>Partner has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 779803</p>			

procurer/partner you represent	defined an open, transparent and non-discriminative administrative framework to select enterprises allowed to test innovative solutions in the “lab” – apart from the case of PCP/PPI?	engagement methodology/experience you have applied or you would like to apply in the management of testing activities in schools? Please comment adding any the key success factor of the applied methodology.	testing activities with businesses in schools? (If yes, please, comment and add relevant law/regulations which could prevent testing activities for instance for security/safety reasons, data protection, ethics, procurement law, education , etc.)
Municipality of Konnevesi	No, but there has been defined framework made in IMAile.	Interaction with the schools and suppliers is important and should take Place from the early start. Our experience from IMAile shows that it's vital that representatives of suppliers are present at school during the testing activities.	The testing activities must be under GDPR. It is important that schools/students/families are aware of the testing and they are informed well of the use of results and other materials (photos, videos, audio). All activities must fit in our educational laws/regulations and procurement law.
SBE (Sara Bedin)	The PCP/PPI doesn't represent an exception. The competition rules should be respected. No discrimination, openness, transparency are general principles...it's in any case a benefit that a Public Authority is assigning to the industries... A call for interest and a selection procedure couldn't be avoided.	Call for interest and selection procedure	All the mentioned regulations are relevant. Including competition law!!!
Viladecans City Council	No	We have previously participated in IMAILE project and we have involved students and teachers in testing in our city. After this experience we are certainly sure that key factors are: teachers skills and complicity, and, useful objectives for educational agents.	Yes. Security/safety, data protection, ethics, and also school schedule In our case the Regional Government has legal educational competences, therefore it will be very important to have their close cooperation.
RSA (Ministerium der Finanzen des Landes Sachsen-Anhalt)	There is no framework, each time it will be decided separately.	The methodologies used were watching the students/teachers during the activity and taking notes and afterwards to provides surveys/questionnaires related to the activity.	The testing activities needs to be compliant to the GDPR (privacy, data protection) and an application at the ministry of education is needed when doing testing activities in schools.
Halmstad	Yes	Establish a test protocol that defines the current situation, what we are going to test and do during the test and what the end result became. Test one activitie at a time.	Yes, a consent form for parents is needed when students attend testing activities. Other, data protection and procurement law.

